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Teachers' Commitment And Job Performance In Public Senior Secondary Schools In Anambra State

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ABSTRACT

The study investigated teachers' commitment and job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlational research design. The population comprised 6420 teachers in the 256 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample of 347 teachers was drawn from 12 schools. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: "Teachers' Commitment Questionnaire (TCQ) and Job Performance Questionnaire (JPQ)" developed by the researchers. The face and content validities of the instruments were done by three experts in the Faculty of Education and Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, which yielded a co-efficient as follows; Teachers' commitment 0.84, punctuality 0.79, instructional materials 0.80 and job performance was 0.80. The research questions were answered using linear regression, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test associated with linear regression. The findings revealed that punctuality and instructional materials related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings of the study, the researchers recommended that principals should ensure that teachers come to school on time and are punctual to class. They should ensure that they put in the time they arrive to work in the time-book and discipline those who report to work late. Also, principal should endeavour to make instructional and teaching materials available in schools. They should ensure that teachers use them well by supervising them while teaching in the classroom, and guiding them on how to use them effectively.

Keywords: Job performance, teachers' commitment, instructional materials

INTRODUCTION

Education is a purposeful activity directed at transmitting knowledge or fostering skills and character traits. It is the transmission of worthy behaviour from one generation to the other. Secondary education is the level of education that comes after primary education. It mediates primary and tertiary education, that is, it comes immediately after primary education and before tertiary education. The secondary education last for about six years. Secondary education is a bridge between primary and tertiary institution and thus holds the compass for the direction any nation intends to follow (Nanbak, 2020). Secondary school being an educational institution is made up of academic staffs who see to it that effective learning process takes place. Teachers are the most important resource in school and the overall success of an educational institution depends on the outcome of teachers' job performances.

Job performance is defined as an individual personal ability to successfully accomplish task allocated to him/her. Job performance is the behavioural outcome of an employee which points out that the employee is showing positive attitude towards his/her organizations. Teachers' job performance is the sum total of the teachers' execution of their tasks which influences students' academic achievement. Teachers' performance predicts school effectiveness, which helps to establish an effective educational system (Ozgenel & Merit 2019). Every educational institution's success depends on its teachers' performance, their commitment to their job is a vital criteria used to assess their performance. Teachers' commitment affect the school effectiveness, this could cause teachers to be less successful in their job performance.

Commitment is defined as the amount of passion, and dedication teachers have towards their work. Teachers' commitment is considered essential because it is the emotional bond a teacher demonstrates towards their work. Teachers' commitment have been recognised as one of the critical factors for effective teaching. Altun (2017) Stated that committed teacher devote time for their students, school and teaching profession. They are responsible for the development of their students and strive to keep the students up and doing. Commitment on the part of teacher reduces withdrawal behaviours like tardiness, absenteeism and turnover. This in turn enhances teachers' dedication to duties and institution's effectiveness. The degree in which teachers commit themselves to their school students, educational activities, profession challenges and society is extremely important (Karluki, et al., 2014). There are things that shows that a teacher is committed, these are elements that shows the commitment of a teacher. They include punctuality, use of instructional materials, exhibiting creative abilities amongst others.

A committed teacher is said to be punctual and always keeping to time. Punctuality can be defined as doing something in the appointed period of time. Time is one of the major parameter to social life, as social life will not be possible if an individual does not have the ability to relate the interaction with time. Teachers' ability to keep to time refers to a strict observation in keeping engagement, promptness (complete stipulated work on time) and commitment which in turn help to enhance their job performance. Teachers' regular attendance in the educational institution usually goes along with punctuality and is referred to as diligent. A committed teacher reports to duty always and does not absent himself deliberately from work. They are always in class to attend to their students as at when due. Punctual teachers plan the works to be done and handle things with lot of seriousness. They see the need to inform the concerned educational authorities about possible delays. Teachers' punctuality facilitate their job performance.

Teachers' ability to use instructional material effectively shows how committed they are. Instructional materials are equipment, devices, objects and formational materials which the teacher uses to facilitate learning process. It is used by teachers in the classroom to make the pupil learn easily and quickly. A committed teacher effectively uses instructional materials to simplify lessons, motivate the learner and make learning meaningful. Lesson can be said to be meaningful if the learners are actively involved in learning activities. A teacher who is able to make learners participate fully in the learning process with the aid of instructional materials is said to be committed.

Problem

The commitment of teachers towards their job is very paramount and important. They are expected to be diligent, dedicated and committed to their job. Teacher job commitment deals with their attitude towards work and this has an influence on the goals achieved in schools. Teachers' commitment to duty is recognized as a crucial factor for enhancing students' academic performance and overall service delivery in the public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. It appears that the work behaviour of some serving teachers in the State schools seem inadequate and unsatisfactory for improving quality education in that level of education. It appears that many teachers are not punctual to schools and come late. Personal observation shows that most of them attend classes late and use little time to teach students. Some do not report to duty over a long period of time and even fail to inform concerned educational authorities about the possible reason for their absence from work. Furthermore, there are concern among parents that their children academic performance is not satisfactory, as some students failed to pass the (2022/2023) WAEC examinations with the required 5 credit pass, including English and Mathematics. Could it be that the poor performance of students in examinations is related to poor teachers' commitment

to duty? This trend has been continuous, it has led the researcher to embark on a research to investigate teachers' commitment and job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study was to investigate teachers' commitment and job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, the objectives sought to:

1. Examine the extent to which teachers' punctuality relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.
2. Determine the extent to which teachers' use of instructional materials relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided this study:

1. To what extent does teachers' punctuality relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State?
2. To what extent does teachers' use of instructional materials relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State?

Hypothesis

The following null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Ho₁: Teachers' punctuality does not significantly relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho₂: Teachers' use of instructional materials does not significantly relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Concept of Teacher

Teaching is an ongoing process that transcends throughout generations, both formally and informally. Any individual can teach, but when it involves transferring ideas and knowledge within an organized structured setting, then that can be ascribed to formal teaching. Teachers are individuals who are trained professionally in the art of teaching and have various teaching techniques, methods and strategies to use in the classroom. Teaching in its broadest sense is the process whereby a teacher guides a learner or a group of learners to a higher level of knowledge or skills. Schlechty (2011) defines teaching as an art of inducing students to behave in ways that are assumed to lead to learning, including an attempt to induce students to so behave. What Schlechty meant by teaching being 'an art' is that the teacher must create situations to facilitate learning and then motivate learners to have interest in what is being transmitted to them. When a teacher teaches, learners pay attention and must comprehend what the teacher is teaching in order to facilitate the teaching and learning process.

Concept of Teacher Commitment

Committed teachers like working with their students and care about their development. These teachers profoundly struggle for efficiency in teaching and learning through employing different approaches. Without love of profession, teaching cannot be conducted effectively. Garrison in Altun (2017) opined that teachers with high level of commitment are in love with teaching. Besides, they have respect for students and it is noteworthy that they build strong relationship with their students which is a hallmark of great teachers. Committed teachers always seek for continuous professional development. It is believed that teachers who have commitment to their profession work collaboratively with other teachers to nurture the learning of the students. Discussing education materials, development of teaching approaches with other teachers in the school inspires teachers to promote intellectual development of their students. These factors not only influence effectiveness of teaching but also efficiency of learning.

It is argued that passion is a need for a high quality education. Passion encourages teachers to act as it is a huge source of motivation (Vallerand, 2007). For that reason, passionate teachers can create excitement for learners to achieve better. Commitment to teaching gives teachers the responsibility to explore constantly new ways of teaching to develop learning experiences of students. Teachers with commitment have the potential to provide students innovative instructional strategies that can lead to better achievement. Moreover, committed teachers through encouraging students to involve in school activities

can create zealous learners. Teacher commitment is highly related to teachers' work performance which has a significant influence on students' achievement. Low level of teachers' commitment reduces students' achievement and vice-versa.

Concept of Teacher Job Performance

Teachers are the backbone of an educational activity. The success and failure of educational activities highly depends on their performance. Their performance is directly linked to process and product of education. Therefore, the performance of teachers is emphatic for the improvement of education. According to Okunola in Muhammad (2013), performance may be described as an act of accomplishing or executing a given task. It could also be described as the ability to combine skilfully the right behaviour towards the achievement of organizational goals and objectives. Teachers' job performance can be described as the duties performed by a teacher at a particular period in the school system in achieving organizational goals. It could also be described as the ability of teachers to combine relevant inputs for the enhancement of teaching and learning processes.

Punctuality and Job Performance

The classroom teacher is the sole manager of the teaching and learning process in a school. The teacher is thus responsible for the outcome of pupils learning. If a teacher must discharge his/her function effectively, he/she must be committed to his/her work. In other words, paramount in the teachers professional practices is the commitment to the growth need and adjustment of learners (Ndifon, 2014). It is therefore obligatory for teachers to ensure that pupils acquire desirable knowledge, values ideas concepts, principles and skills necessary for the overall growth, development and academic performance. The execution of such obligations is expressed in his/her teaching behavior and seriousness with which he/she handles his instructions. Teaching involves a reciprocal contact between the teacher and students. It covers the purpose dimension, the information dimension and the measurement and evaluation dimension. Commitment to quality teaching therefore is important for the teacher. Such a commitment takes into consideration the mastery of the subject matter, including the criteria for selection such as, validity, significance, ability, interest and learners abilities Isangedighi in Ndifon (2014). Effective teaching cannot be guaranteed without commitments to work and commitment to students' characteristics. Isangedighi in Ndifon (2014) further added that the teachers' knowledge of the learner's characteristics should cover the areas of talent, intelligence, skills, home background and their hereditary assets and liabilities.

Teachers' punctuality to school is a vital factor or sub-variable of teachers attitude to work, which can affect academic performance of pupils. In other words, teachers who are always punctual to school can instill such attitude in pupils, and this can result in good academic performance of the pupils. According to Alexander in Ndifon (2014), by the Guyana law, teachers are required to report for duty at least fifteen minutes before the start of lesson each day in order to prepare and to be ready to start work promptly. Unfortunately, some teachers do not always observe this. When teachers are absent or frequently come late to school, they deprive the learners the opportunity of experiencing full explanation of concepts. If the students are fortunate to have a particular lesson repeated, it might be an abbreviated version of the original lesson and at the expense of the later lessons, since teacher at this time will be in a hurry to cover up the syllabus so as to meet up with time.

This situation according to Alexander in Ndifon (2014) results in under-achievement of students which may also lead to an increase in drop-out rate; thereby affecting negatively, parents' zeal to spend more money sending their children to school. According to Hazeltine in Ndifon (2014), there are several reasons why there may be a difference in the recording of lateness among teachers. Teachers are different, while one may arrive school and quickly move into the classroom to get ready for the day's job, another may find all kinds of distractions on the way to school. Also, another may have more parents waiting to speak to him in the morning so that when they arrive school, it is later than 8:30 am. In all of this Hazaltine in Ndidon (2014) therefore advised that teachers should bear in mind that being punctual is a part of showing courtesy, which is a part of love, and a way people can express love and respect towards one another. It is also added that there are some differences in the way lateness is handled in school. Not only must teachers be on time in the morning, they must also be on time for each class during the day.

With seven periods in a day and very specific time for each, the potential for disruption grows geometrically. According to Ndifon (2014), punctuality therefore is an important life skill for the world of work, as it is not uncommon for teachers to be sent home or fired from work for showing up late always.

In most secondary schools in Nigeria, teachers are supposed to resume in a school on or before 8.00 am (7.30 am in the case of primary school). A teacher is expected to write his/her name on the Time-Book (one of the school records), indicate the time he/she arrives in school, and complete the process by appending his/her signature after the time indicated (Ige & Omotayo, 2020). A teacher who comes after the normal time (8.00 am or 7.30 am) is deemed to have come late to school that day. Lateness is a form of activity that students and teachers partake in. It refers to a situation whereby individuals report to their duties or appointments later than the usual time. Nakpodia & Dafiaghor (2011) see it as the situation where an individual arrives after the proper, scheduled, or usual time. Lauby (2009) added that it is a situation of not showing up on time. Also, Breezes (2010) view it as being synonymous with "tardiness", i.e. being slow to act or respond, thus not meeting up with proper or usual timing. In this study, lateness is seen as a delay in getting to school by teachers. Lateness to school relates simply to the failure to be present at the appropriate time for school activities/ lesson, according to Ige and Omotayo (2020), a teacher is therefore considered late to school if he/she fails to sign the Time-Book at the appropriate time. The proper time in this context is before the Time Book is ruled-off by the Principal or officer designated to do so. It is also important to note that even if a teacher is physically present in a school at the appropriate time but fails to sign the Time-Book, he/she could be considered to be late to school. This is because the Time Book is the administrative instrument used for controlling attendance issues in schools (Ige & Omotayo).

Another survey indicated that teacher lateness was a major obstacle to effective and sustainable implementation of the country's education system where the lateness rate was 10% at the primary and 13% at the secondary schools (Uwezo 2011). Also, African Economic Research Consortium's Service Delivery (2011) found that teacher lateness rate in Nigeria was 23% in Public Secondary Schools. The report also indicated that in Nigeria, teacher lateness was lower in the private schools than in public schools while the rate was higher among the contract teachers than the permanent teachers (Crocetti, 2014).

Instructional Materials and Job Performance

Teaching materials also known as teaching aids are tools and equipment used in teaching as a supplement in class room instruction to enhance the interest of students. Teaching materials are important catalysts of effective instructions. Besides the traditional teaching methods, there are wide varieties of teaching aids available to the teacher. They help students to improve reading and other skill. In the present age of sciences and technology, the process of teaching and learning also depends on the latest technology. Teaching becomes interesting when a teacher uses different teaching materials because it directly involves student in the teaching- learning process. It makes lessons enjoyable and memorable. Teaching materials are key factor in creating effective teaching and learning environments. These aids directly address to the five senses so the chances of forgetting become less and process of learning becomes more effective.

According to Kapur (2015), to teach a new language, different teaching materials should be used in order to enhance learners' learning process so that the learner may be able to communicate the learned language in real life. Linguistics now encourages the use of teaching materials in teaching because of their positive effects on students. The use of teaching materials in class is important because it has gained much more attention around the world. As a result, effective materials become need of the time. To teach a language using text book is regarded artificial because it cannot connect the students to the second language.

Type of Instructional Materials

There are many different types of instructional materials that can be used in class. Kapur (2015) Stated the following as types of instructional materials:

Visual: Visual aids use sense of vision. It includes actual objects, charts, maps, flash cards, pictures, flannel board, white board, flip charts, models etc.

Audio: Audio aids are common teaching tools which include classroom stereo system, individual head sets, radio etc. In languages class, teachers use recordings to demonstrate how the language is spoken. It is used as a recreational activity. It involves the sense of hearing.

Audio Visual: These aids can have a great impact on teaching. It involves the sense of vision as well as hearing. Audio Video aids are multi sensory materials. They can be produced, distributed and used as planned components of education program. Teachers can use instructional or documentary video to enhance specific subject or topic. It usually requires television, digital video player, projection, film strips etc.

Mobile Technology: Mobile technology is everywhere. Mobile learning is relatively less expensive opportunity. It is convenient as it is accessible from anywhere. In the classroom it can replace traditional mode of teaching which create boredom. A mobile device provides information inside or outside the class so there is all time connection between friends and teacher. It gives new opportunities to both teacher and student.

Language games: It develops the basic skills i.e. listening, speaking, reading and writing. It also develops self confidence and communication skill of the students.

Language Lab: It is modern teaching method used as audio or audio visual aids. Variety of listening and speaking skills are exposed to the students. It is provided with computer, video, electronic testing, word games, quizzes, debates etc.

News Paper: It develops students reading skill. Selection of newspaper material is also very important because it strengthens creative writing, knowledge of structure and grammar. A teacher can make it interesting by giving different task to the students.

Improvisation: Improvisation is useful in teaching at the higher level. Gur – Ze've (2015) says: *“Improvisation, when true to itself, transcends any limited context, border, dogma, regulations, drives, habits and fears dwelling in the moment of the ecstasies of the here and now”*. He further stressed that improvisation is not rhetorical, rational and ethnical in the traditional western concept of knowledge and inter-subjectivity.

Improvisation is an interaction which can improve students' communicative ability. It directly enhances languages skills, real life communication in a student. They enjoy learning in play way method through imitation, dramatizing, singing, dancing etc. It is a natural aid without any cost.

Importance of instructional materials

Teaching is a social activity and it is not possible to teach students without taking part in this process. A teacher and a student should both be involved in this activity to perform better. Instructional materials are very important instruments in the teaching process which can involve both of them. The importance according to Babajide (2010) includes the following:

1. Instructional materials make lessons more enjoyable, clear and comprehensible for students. They can be used at all levels of learning process to enrich vocabulary and knowledge.
2. Instructional materials for second language motivates the students so that they can learn a language easily without having any difficulty.
3. Instructional materials are effective to increase student's memory. What they learn with the help of these aids imprints in their mind. It also makes their learning permanent. Supportive teaching materials provide advantages to remember the second language better.
4. Instructional materials can facilitate the better understanding of the subject which discourages the act of confusion. It makes the subject and every aspect of lesson very clear and makes them successful in learning second language process.
5. Activities used during the teaching of language make their learning process like a game and students enjoy the learning process. The more use of supportive materials increases the learning activities and chances of success.
6. Use of instructional materials is absolutely effective because it makes the whole process simple, productive and enrich the learning activities.
7. These materials also increase student's interest and motivate them to learn a second language better.

8. These materials also provide a natural learning atmosphere and help them to actively involve themselves in the learning, teaching and experiencing process.
9. Use of instructional materials in the class can heighten students' desire for learning. All the students participate in the learning process vividly. It enables the students to express their concepts effectively.
10. Instructional materials make the class room lively, active and devoid of dullness because of involvement of every student. It provides direct experience to the students.
11. Use of proper instructional materials saves lots of time and money also. It saves time from long and boring explanatory class and helps the students to understand the complex subjects easily.

Instructional materials provided in schools must be adequately provided to ensure proper use by the teachers. It is not enough to provide instructional materials but ensuring from time to time that they are in good shape is essential and vital. Any facility or equipment that is not properly maintained would depreciate and finally wear out. Every teacher and student has it as their rights to enjoy basic facilities provided in the schools. These facilities should be properly maintained to enable the teachers and students derive maximum satisfaction from their utilization.

The Three Component Theory

The theory that was adopted in this study was the three-component theory of organizational commitment by Allen and Meyer (1990). The theory States that organizational commitment is of three distinctive components which are the affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment. They are components that explain how organizations work as regards to their commitments. The affective commitment States the emotional attachment of an employee to an organization. If workers have a high level of affective commitment, they enjoy their relationship with the organization and are likely to stay. These workers stay with an organization because they want to stay. while normative commitment is the degree to which an employee feels responsible and obligated to stay with an organization because they perceive as the right thing to do. Normatively committed employees feel that leaving their organization would have a negative effect on the organization and the workers, and feel a sense of guilt around the idea of leaving. Lastly, the third dimension which is the continuance commitment is the degree to which employees believe that leaving the organization would be personally inconvenient and costly. If an employee has a high level of continuance commitment, they will stay with an organization because they feel that they must stay. For example, an employee may feel that quitting their job may lead to an unacceptable length of unemployment, there may be a lack of good work alternatives, as well as concerns with the potential salaries being offered to them by similar organizations and so on.

This theory is related to this study because the school is an organization and so the commitment of teachers is very paramount in the achievement and attainment of goals.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted correlational research design. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The population comprised 6420 teachers in the 256 public senior secondary schools in Anambra State. A sample of 347 teachers was drawn from 12 schools. The instrument used for data collection was a self-structured questionnaire titled: "Teachers' Commitment Questionnaire (TCQ) and Job Performance Questionnaire (JPQ)" developed by the researcher. The face and content validities of the instruments were done by three experts in the Faculty of Education and Cronbach Alpha statistics was used to determine the internal consistency of the instrument, which yielded a co-efficient as follows; Teachers' commitment 0.84, punctuality 0.79, instructional materials 0.80 and job performance was 0.80. The research questions were answered using linear regression, while the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test associated with linear regression.

RESULTS

Research Question 1: *To what extent does teachers’ punctuality relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 1: Linear Regression Analysis on the Extent Punctuality relates to Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism
1	0.797	.635	0.633	63.5%

Table 1 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.797 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.635. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it showed that punctuality related to job performance by 63.5% while the remaining 36.5% was accounted for by other variables. It showed that the extent to which punctuality related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State was high.

Research Question 2: *To what extent does teachers’ use of instructional materials relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State?*

Table 2: Linear Regression Analysis on the Extent Instructional Materials relate to Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Coefficient of determinism
1	0.720	0.518	0.516	51.8%

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.720 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.518. Judging by the coefficient of determinism, it showed that instructional materials related to job performance by 51.8% while the remaining 48.2% was accounted for by other variables. It showed that the extent to which instructional materials related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State was high.

Hypotheses

Hypothesis 1: Teachers’ punctuality does not significantly relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 3: t-test Associated with Linear Regression on the Extent Punctuality relates to Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	103.212	0.620		21.236	0.000
	Punctuality	196	0.096	0.797	1.270	0.000

Table 3 showed that the value of t-test associated with the simple regression was 21.236 at a p-value level of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05 and on this note, the null hypothesis was not retained while the alternative hypothesis was upheld implying that punctuality significantly related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

Hypothesis 2: Teachers’ use of instructional materials does not significantly relate to their job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State

Table 4: t-test Associated with Linear Regression on the Extent Instructional Materials relates to Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Coefficients Beta		
1	(Constant)	123.303	0.5840		33.911	0.000
	Instructional materials	0.096	0.046	0.720	1.265	0.000

Table 4 showed that the value of t-test associated with the simple regression was 33.911 at a p-value level of 0.000 which was less than the alpha value of 0.05 and on this note, the null hypothesis was not retained while the alternative hypothesis was upheld implying that instructional materials significantly related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State.

DISCUSSION

To what extent does Teachers' Punctuality relate to their Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

The first findings of the study revealed that punctuality related to job performance by 63.5% while the remaining 36.5% was accounted for by other variables. It showed a high extent. This implied that punctuality related to job performance. This finding is in agreement with that of Ndifon (2014), who stated that by the Guyana law, teachers are required to report for duty at least fifteen minutes before the start of lesson each day in order to prepare and to be ready to start work promptly. This would enable them prepare well and attend to the needs of students. It would also determine their performance in schools. If a teacher must discharge his/her function effectively, he/she must be committed to his/her work. This also agrees with the Statement of Ndifon (2014) who opined that paramount in the teachers professional practices is the commitment to the growth need and adjustment of learners (Ndifon, 2014).

Research by Ige and Omtayo (2020) revealed that a teacher is expected to write his/her name on the Time-Book (one of the school records), indicate the time he/she arrives in school, and complete the process by appending his/her signature after the time indicated (Ige & Omtayo, 2020). This also determines their job performance in schools. The respondents agreed that punctuality has a high prediction with the performance of teachers and this can be achieved in schools when they report to work on time, sign in the register note and commence lesson on time. The outcome of teacher punctuality to school cannot be over-emphasized and their lateness also has an adverse effect of not only on their performance, but on the academic performance of students.

To what Extent does teachers' use of Instructional Materials relate to their Job Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Anambra State?

In this study, it was established that there is a relationship between instructional materials and job performance by 51.8% while the remaining 48.2% was accounted for by other variables, it equally showed that the extent to which instructional materials related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State was high. Instructional materials are important in the teaching and learning process. Teaching becomes interesting when a teacher uses different teaching materials because it directly involves student in the teaching- learning process. It makes lessons enjoyable and memorable. Teaching materials are key factor in creating effective teaching and learning environments. This finding is in agreement with Hyland (2012) who stated that one of the most important advantages of using instructional materials is that it increases learners' motivation and reflects positively on their learning process.

Instructional materials provided in schools must be adequately provided to ensure proper use by the teachers. It is not enough to provide instructional materials but ensuring from time to time that they are in good shape is essential and vital. They must be used well in order to achieve the set goals. In many schools, instructional materials are not well utilized and teachers who do not know how to use them will not enhance their performance. This is in agreement with Ugwuanyi (2013) who posited that one of the factors contributing to non-utilization of physical facilities in education in Nigeria is due to lack of maintenance. Instructional materials have been discovered to determine the job performance of teachers

in schools. They help to facilitate the teaching and learning process and also help students perform well in their academics. This can only be achieved if teachers learn how to use them well and properly.

Findings

1. Punctuality significantly related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State by 63.5%
2. Instructional materials significantly related to job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State by 51.8%.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study it was concluded that punctuality had the highest influence on teacher job performance in public senior secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. This implies that teachers' punctuality to school and carrying out their tasks on time had more influence on their job performance.

RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Principals should ensure that teachers come to school on time and are punctual to class. They should ensure that they put in the time they arrive to work to in the time-book and discipline those who report to work late.
2. Principals should endeavour to make instructional and teaching materials available in schools. They should ensure that teachers use them well by supervising them while teaching in the classroom, and guiding them on how to use them effectively.

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